

A Study of a Method of Determination of Nickel in Presence of Iodine and its Determination in Presence of Cobalt

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This paper describes an investigation of the appropriate method for the nickel determination.

The complexes of nickel-oximes (dimethylglyoxime, 1,2 cycle. hexandiondioxime (nioxime) and α -furildioxime) extracted to a small extent by chloroform from acidic medium (pH 1-3), have not any peak in visible region, which means that the determination of nickel by this method is not practicable.

In the presence of iodine the complexes of nickel-oxime in acidic medium shows absorption peaks. But adding sodium thiosulphate, in order to get rid of excess of the iodine, and shaking the organic solution for a short time would cause these peaks to disappear. The complex of nickel-dimethylglyoxime and the complex of nickel-nioxime in alkaline medium were extracted by chloroform and exhibited a considerable absorption in visible region, but no peak in the visible region was observed when iodine was added.

The complex of nickel- α -furildioxime with and without iodine exhibits a remarkable absorption in the visible region (440-460 nm). This peak does not disappear when the excess of iodine is destroyed by sodium thiosulphate.

IN the different materials, nickel often contains cobalt. The exact determination of nickel depends on the formation of a complex compound with a proper reagent and complete extraction of this complex with organic solvents. Many reagents have been used in the determination of nickel, some of these are oximes. Cobalt also forms complexes with these reagents, so it was found interesting the investigation of nickel complexes in the presence of iodine in order to find a specific method for the determination of nickel and or to reduce the influence of cobalt.

Reagents which have been used in the determination of nickel are: dimethyl glyoxime, salicylaldehyde, methyl nioxime and pyridine¹. Previous studies²⁻⁵ have shown that the oximes such as α -furil-monoxime, α -furildioxime, 1,2-cyclohexandiondioxime (nioxime) and dimethylglyoxime are suitable reagents for the determination and separation of nickel and cobalt.

Dimethylglyoxime has been used for the determination of nickel in the absence of elements which form complexes with dimethylglyoximes especially cobalt, copper and bismuth. Until now, there has been no method available for the separation of dimethylglyoxime complexes of iron, cobalt and nickel in the presence of iodine. Our study has exploited the separation by such a method to study the nature of these complexes in the presence of iodine, and to determine the nickel in the presence of a large quantity of cobalt. The maximum amount of cobalt-dimethylglyoxime, which can be extracted by chloroform equals 7% from an acidic medium pH 1-3;

this percentage decreases when the medium of the aqueous phase is alkaline.

The determination of nickel-dimethylglyoxime cannot be effected in the presence of cobalt even if present in the ratio Ni/Co=1/250, but when this ratio increases the error of the results increases to 10%.

The investigation of cobalt-dimethylglyoximes from the aqueous phase (pH $\approx$ 9) in the presence of (Tartaric) acid, showed that the extraction percentage was very small and equalled to 0.80%. This characteristic can be used for decreasing the effect of cobalt in a ratio of Ni/Co = 1/250 with an error of $\pm 4\%$. The determination of nickel in the presence of a large quantity of cobalt was done by separating cobalt with ammonium thiocyanate (NH₄SCN). The complex of thiocyanate cobalt was extracted by ethyl acetate, the excess thiocyanate destroyed by nitric acid, and then the nickel determined by dimethylglyoxime as before. This method showed that nickel could be determined in the presence of cobalt in a ratio of Ni/Co = 1/2000 with error $\pm 3.5\%$.³

Nioxime is used for the determination of micro quantities of nickel in the presence of large quantities of foreign cations; the nioxime complex of nickel is extracted with organic solvents. Nioxime cobalt (II) complex is slightly soluble in chloroform but is more soluble in iso-amyl alcohol. The extraction of the nioxime cobalt complex in the presence of an oxidant (NaNO₂ or I₂) at pH $\approx$ 9 and not complete by using either chloroform or iso-amyl alcohol, but it could be completely extracted from an acidic

medium ($pH \approx 1$) in the presence of iodine by using a mixture of chloroform and iso-amyl alcohol (3 : 1). Nioxime and iodine have proved to be superior in the selective determination of cobalt for the complete extraction of cobalt from an acidic medium, 98%.

The presence of nickel does not affect the percentage of extraction of cobalt even if they are in a ratio of $Co/Ni = 1/10000$. The use of this system for the determination of cobalt has several advantages among which is that nickel does form a complex with nioxime in the presence of iodine but does not have maximum absorption at 460 nm. In previous work the use of nioxime and iodine has proved to be superior in the selective determination of cobalt, for the difference in the characteristic of the complex of nickel with nioxime and the complex of cobalt with nioxime in the presence of iodine. In the present work nioxime nickel-iodine has been proved to be impracticable for the determination of nickel.

α -Furildioxime has been proposed for the determination of nickel, it gives a red precipitate with nickel salt in an ammoniacal solution; the complex is less soluble than nickel dimethylglyoxime, thus giving a large weight of precipitate for a given weight of nickel. The great advantage of α -furildioxime is the solubility in water which precludes the possibility of contaminating the precipitate of the nickel derivative with the free reagent. In previous work³ it was proved that α -furildioxime was useful only for the determination of pure nickel, so it was necessary to investigate the complex of this reagent with nickel in the presence of iodine. All the results of the investigation of nickel—nioxime—iodine in acidic and alkaline media do not show any peak for this complex in a visible region.

Until now there has been no method available for the separation and determination of nickel in the presence of cobalt by using the α -furildioxime—iodine reagent. One study has exploited the determination of nickel by such a method to study the nature of those complexes in the presence of iodine.

Experimental

1. *A solution of 0.1 N Iodine*: Weighed exactly 8.300 g. of KI dissolves in 30–40 ml. of water in a glass stoppered 250 ml. flask. Weigh about 3.18 g. of iodine on a rough balance and transfer it by means of a small dry funnel into KI solution, shake until all the iodine has dissolved after cooling to room temperature, make up the volume with water.

2. *Stock aqueous solution of nickel*: Weigh exactly (28.06 g.) of $NiSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O$ and dissolve it in 100–200 ml. water in a glass-stoppered 1000 ml. flask, shake until all the nickel salt has dissolved, then add 200 ml. conc. HCl and after cooling to room temperature make up to volume with water.

3. *Buffer solutions*: Buffer solutions ($pH \approx 9$) were prepared from ammonium acetate, ($pH \approx 2$) from 0.05M hydrochloric acid potassium chloride⁶.

4. Reagents :

- Dimethylglyoxime : 0.1M in ethanol.
- Nioxime (m.p. 189°) was obtained from Aldrich Chemical Co. Inc. A white crystalline compound, 0.1M solution of nioxime in water was prepared.
- 0.1M of α -furildioxime (molecular weight = 220.19, weighing exactly 2.2019 g.) was dissolved in water and made up to volume with water in glass stoppered 100 ml. flask.

The spectrophotometric measurements were carried on by (Unim A.P. 600 series 2) with a cell of 1 cm. length. The pH meter was Model 38B Electronic Instruments Ltd., England. Results were treated statistically.⁷

Results and Discussion

A. The complex of nickel with oxime series in an acidic medium

The aqueous mixture of 0.1M of nickel (1 ml.) buffer solution ($pH 1$) (5 ml.) and dimethylglyoxime (4 ml.) was shaken with 10 ml. of chloroform for 1 hr and then allowed to separate. This organic solution was measured spectrophotometrically at different wavelengths for the optical sensitivity. The spectra of nioxime-nickel, and α -furildioxime were measured in the acidic medium. It was concluded that complexes of these oximes with no absorption could be detected in the visible region (Fig. 1); so the determination of nickel by these oximes was not practicable. However, further investigations of this complex are being carried out.

Fig. 1. The absorption spectra of the complex of nickel with oxime series in acidic medium :

- Complex of dimethylglyoxime—nickel.
- Complex of nioxime—nickel.
- Complex of α -furildioxime—nickel.

B. The complexes of nickel with the oxime series in acidic medium and in the presence of iodine

Preparation of these complexes has been carried out with the same procedure as in the former cases² except the addition of 1 ml. of iodine and the reagent (3 ml.). The organic layer was measured spectro-

photometrically at different wave lengths for the optical density. (Fig. 2, graph No. 1, 2, and 3).

Fig. 2. The absorption spectra of the complexes of nickel with the oxime series in acidic medium and in presence of iodine :

1. Complex of dimethylglyoxime—nickel—iodine
2. Complex of nioxime—nickel—iodine.
3. Complex of α -furildioxime—nickel—iodine.
4. Complex of dimethylglyoxime—nickel—iodine.
5. Complex of nioxime—nickel—iodine.
6. Complex of α -furildioxime—nickel—iodine.
7. Excess of iodine was destroyed with sodium thiosulphate.

The organic layer of each complex was transferred to another separating funnel containing solid sodium thiosulphate (2 g.) and shaken for five minutes to destroy the excess iodine, the organic phase was separated from sodium thiosulphate and measured spectrophotometrically at different wave lengths for the optical density (Fig. 2, graph 4, 5 and 6).

We can see from Fig. 2, graph 1, 2 and 3, that an absorption peak was detected in the visible region in the spectrum of dimethylglyoxime-nickel-iodine (510–520 nm) in the spectrum of α -furildioxime-nickel-iodine (500–530 nm) and the absorption peak which was detected at the visible region in the spectrum of nioxime-nickel-iodine at 560 nm. It can be seen also from Fig. 2, graph 5 and 6, that no spectrum has a peak in the visible region, but in the spectrum of nioxime-nickel-iodine, a marked peak was detected at (460–480 nm), however, this peak disappeared after a short time. So the determination of nickel by this procedure was not practicable.

C. *The complex of nickel with the oxime series in an alkaline medium and in the presence of iodine*

Our intention here is to investigate the effect of the medium on the stability of the complex nickel with the oxime series and in the presence of iodine. The same procedure was carried out as in former cases except the medium of aqueous solutions from which the complexes of these oxime-nickel-iodine by chloroform were extracted and were measured spectrophotometrically (Fig. 3, graphs 1, 2 and 3 without iodine), (graphs 4, 5 and 6 in the presence of iodine), and the graph 7 was measured after destroying the excess of iodine.

From these graphs we can see at a marked absorption in the visible region (370–380 nm), in the spectrum of dimethylglyoxime-nickel-iodine. The

peak of the complex of nioxime-nickel was detected at (460 nm) and disappeared in the presence of iodine (graph 2 and 5). From graphs 3 and 6 we can see that the marked absorption in the visible region in the spectrum of α -furildioxime in the presence of iodine and without iodine (390–460 nm), the density of the spectrum of this complex-presence of iodine is little higher than that without iodine. However, when the excess of iodine is destroyed by sodium thiosulphate, the absorption peak is also shown at the visible region (440–460 nm). So the stability of this complex, the effect of time and the

Fig. 3. The absorption spectra of the complexes of nickel with oxime series in alkaline medium.

1. Complex of dimethylglyoxime—nickel.
2. Complex of nioxime—nickel.
3. Complex of α -furildioxime—nickel.
4. Complex of dimethylglyoxime—nickel—iodine.
5. Complex of nioxime—nickel—iodine.
6. Complex of α -furildioxime—nickel—iodine.
7. As in (6) but the excess of iodine was destroyed with sodium thiosulphate.

reagents were investigated and all results indicated that we could use α -furildioxime for the determination of micro amount of nickel alone or in the presence of a great quantity of cobalt. For this purpose five separating funnels were prepared as follows :

Each funnel contains the solution of nickel of different concentrations (0.0–1.5 g/ml), 2 ml. iodine, 5 ml. buffer solution ($pH \approx 9$) and 3 ml. of α -furildioxime, the aqueous phase (15 ml.) plus (15 ml.) organic solvent.

After extracting this mixture for one hour, the organic phase was collected and filtered, the excess of iodine was destroyed by $Na_2S_2O_3$ as before. The optical density of this organic phase was measured at $\lambda = 450 m$ including the blank.

The complex of cobalt, iron and copper α -furildioxime in presence of iodine in alkaline medium do not show any maximum peak in the visible region, and have practically no absorption at this region, while that of nickel has a peak in $\lambda = 450 ml$.

The best percentage extraction with α -furildioxime-iodine reagent can be achieved by using the organic mixture of isoamyl alcohol and chloroform (1 : 3 v/v) in alkaline medium ($pH \approx 9$). The percentage of the

TABLE 1

N	Conc. of Ni mg/ml	x_i				$\bar{x} = \frac{\sum x_i}{n}$	$S^2 = \frac{\sum(x_i - \bar{x})^2}{n-1}$	$S \cdot 10^3$	$t\alpha, k$ $\alpha = 0.35$	$\frac{t\alpha k \cdot S}{\sqrt{n}}$	Warranty interval $\bar{x} \pm \frac{t\alpha \cdot S}{\sqrt{n}}$
		D_1	D_2	D_3	D_4						
4	0.01	0.14	0.10	0.12	0.12	2.66×10^{-4}	16.33	2.77	0.0226	0.12 ± 0.0226	
4	0.02	0.25	0.25	0.24	0.26	0.66×10^{-4}	8.12	2.77	0.01125	0.25 ± 0.01125	
4	0.03	0.42	0.44	0.40	0.34	5.66×10^{-4}	23.80	2.77	0.03296	0.42 ± 0.03296	
4	0.04	0.55	0.53	0.53	0.54	1.66×10^{-4}	12.88	2.77	0.01788	0.53 ± 0.01788	

extraction does not change even if Ni/Co or Ni/Fe or Ni/Cu ratio is 1/10000. (Table 1 and 2).

The spectrophotometric measurements were made and results were treated statistically.

TABLE 2—THE EFFECT OF CO, FE AND CU ON THE DETERMINATION OF NI

Ratio	The optical densities of:			
	Ni	Ni/Co	Ni/Fe	Ni/Cu
1 : 1	0.42	0.41	0.41	0.40
1 : 10	0.42	0.43	0.41	0.44
1 : 100	0.44	0.43	0.45	0.42
1 : 1000	0.45	0.44	0.43	0.42
1 : 10000	0.40	0.39	0.41	0.39

Conc. of Ni (0.02 mg/ml), while that of the others are (2 mg/ml).

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